

A network diagram background consisting of a complex web of interconnected nodes and lines. The nodes are represented by circles of varying sizes and colors, including shades of blue, grey, and white. The lines connecting them are thin and light blue, creating a dense, interconnected structure that suggests a network or a system of relationships.

D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan with Consultation Guide

March 2023

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the processes of stakeholder mapping and engagement plan for the ENERGATE project. The stakeholder mapping process involves identifying relevant stakeholders to be involved in the co-creation process of the platform and those relevant for communication purposes for further uptake. The first step involved identifying the primary stakeholders that are essential to the project's success ([Chapter 2.1](#)) which have been divided into a supply-side segment (those who can input data of their building projects into the platform) and demand-side (those who are looking for investment opportunities).

The second step required prioritizing stakeholders based on their interest and perceived ability to influence the project outcome ([Chapter 2.2](#)). This was achieved using a power-interest grid that classifies stakeholders into four categories: high power/high interest, high power/low interest, low power/high interest, and low power/low interest. This was combined with an assessment of the outreach of each partner within the consortium to have an estimate of the outreach potential ([Chapter 2.3](#)), where the consortium estimated to have an outreach to 382 stakeholders.

The ENERGATE project's engagement plan ([Chapter 3](#)) consists of four actions to involve internal and external stakeholders continuously throughout the project. The first action involves semi-structured interviews with the pilot partners in the consortium to establish the requirements from stakeholders for using the ENERGATE platform. The second action involves surveys with external stakeholders to gather feedback on the user-needs based on inputs from a larger group of stakeholders who are not part of the consortium. The third action involves organizing four regional training workshops to present the developments and outcomes of the project as well as go into detail on the platform's functionalities. The final action involves organizing a final event to showcase the project's results to a broader audience.

1. Introduction

This deliverable describes two essential processes for the ENERGATE:

- 1) **Stakeholder Mapping:** It is essential to identify which target groups should be involved in the co-design process and feedback loop that feeds into the development of the ENERGATE platform (feeding into WPs 2, 3, 4 & 6) and which stakeholders are relevant to communicate the results to for further uptake (feeding into WP7). A preliminary analysis has already been done during the proposal-writing stage of the ENERGATE project and has been further examined and elaborated since the start of the project with inputs from the whole consortium.
- 2) **Engagement Plan:** With a clearer picture on which target groups that ENERGATE should target for which purposes, an action plan needs to be laid down on how they will be engaged throughout the project, linking into many other activities of the project. This engagement plan primarily focuses on the target groups that should be involved into the co-creation process and feedback loop of the ENERGATE platform. The action plan to engage stakeholders that are relevant for communication purposes for the further uptake of the results is laid down in D7.1.

The objective of this document is to identify *who* are the right stakeholders, *why* they need to be involved and *how* they will participate in the successful delivery of the project. To ensure a positive result delivery it is essential to engage the relevant stakeholders especially during the first stage to gain feedback and improve the platform. Developing a well-structured stakeholder engagement process involves identifying stakeholders relevant for the co-creation process, see how we should involve them at different stages, and based on that develop an engagement plan.

This report will first briefly introduce the task and the relationship with the other work packages. Secondly, Chapter 2 details the methodology used for the stakeholder mapping. Chapter 3 focuses on the stakeholder engagement plan followed by Chapter 4, that presents risk and barriers to overcome. Chapter 5 will present a conclusion, presenting the results of stakeholder identification with an overview of the pilot projects in Greece, Italy, Latvia, Austria, France, and Spain.

1.1. Methodology

The Stakeholder Mapping feeds into Engagement as the identification of what type stakeholders are the most relevant for co-creation workshop & interviews, after which we can lay down the plan on how to engage them. The purpose of the plan is to achieve the objectives outlined in the introduction.

This will involve three key steps:

Figure 1. Methodology Overview

With this in mind, the following steps were implemented chronologically – sometimes in parallel – to write this deliverable:

1. **Identification of relevant stakeholders:** It is important to identify relevant stakeholders in the project as they are the key players who can influence the success or failure of the project. A preliminary list of stakeholders was identified based on previous project results, and further defined through a structured discussion at the Kick-off Meeting. This process ensures that all important stakeholders are identified and considered from the outset of the project.
2. **Categorisation of stakeholders:** Categorising stakeholders is important to better understand their specific interests and needs, as well as the potential impact they could have on the project. This allows for a more tailored approach to stakeholder engagement, enabling the project team to focus on the stakeholders that are most important to the project's success. The initial categorisation of stakeholders was made during the Kick-off Meeting and was refined through further discussion and feedback from the consortium partners.
3. **Analysis of stakeholder interests & influence:** Understanding stakeholder interests and influence is crucial to developing effective communication strategies that resonate with them. By outlining the different target groups, why the project is beneficial for them, and what message should be conveyed, the project team can ensure that stakeholders are engaged in a meaningful way. Additionally, the survey conducted by REHVA allowed for an assessment of stakeholder interest and influence, providing valuable insights for developing effective stakeholder engagement plans.
4. **Analysis of outreach to stakeholders:** It is important to understand the outreach that each consortium partner has to the different primary stakeholder groups to assess where the consortium has a stronger outreach and in which countries. This enables the project team to develop targeted communication strategies to reach out to stakeholders where outreach is weak, ensuring that all stakeholders are reached in an effective way.
5. **Fine-tune engagement plan:** The stakeholder analysis allows for the development of an engagement plan that uses the right combination of methods to engage stakeholders in both qualitative and quantitative ways. This ensures that stakeholders are engaged in a way that is most relevant and effective for them, leading to better project outcomes.
6. **Monitor and adjust:** Continuously monitoring stakeholder engagement and adjusting the engagement plan as needed is crucial to ensure that stakeholder needs are being addressed and the project is on track. This enables the project team to adapt to changing stakeholder needs and preferences, leading to better stakeholder engagement and project outcomes.

In the following chapters we will analyse in depth the described steps.

1.2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The engagement plan is a central part in reaching stakeholders that can be involved with project results. A list of KPIs has been laid down to measure the success of stakeholder

engagement that the activities described in this report (see Chapter 3) will implement, together with the implementation of other WPs such as communication and dissemination. The table below describes the measurable indicators with a brief explanation on how the consortium aims to complete this:

Table 1. Overview table of KPIs and implementation.

Target	Implementation
Identification of at least 350 key stakeholders	Setup of repository of stakeholder contact list at consortium level. Preliminary estimation by the full consortium is at least 382 stakeholders identified during first months of the project, already exceeding the target.
40-50 (in total) country experts participated in the bottom-up consultation process	Involvement of country/national experts in the activities described in the engagement plan (see Chapter 3)
Bilateral meetings/calls organised with stakeholders	Continuously throughout the project, all consortium members will meet with both internal and external stakeholders about ENERGATE results.
Webinar series organised across participating countries to present ENERGATE platform (at least one per participating country)	Organisation of national level webinars per participating country and an EU-wide webinar (in English) organised by REHVA and IEECP (see Chapter 3)
At least 7 high-qualified experts members of the ENERGATE Advisory Board	Setup of advisory board and involvement in different activities described in engagement plan (see Chapter 3)
20 – 30 key stakeholders in each Regional Training Workshop	Organisation of 4 Regional Training Workshops throughout the project (between M6 – M30) as described in engagement plan (see Chapter 3).

1.3. Communication channels for stakeholders

When it comes to communication channels, it's advisable to treat stakeholders from different groups similarly. Direct engagement with stakeholders is highly recommended, as face-to-face meetings are invaluable. However, due to the number of stakeholders involved, direct meetings should only be used as needed, mainly with stakeholders from the third group (outlined below). The way in which initial contact is made should be tailored to the existing relationship that a partner has with a potential stakeholder.

Partners' relationships with potential stakeholders can be classified into three groups, each with different communication channels:

- a) **Stakeholders with LoS:** In the event that a stakeholder has already submitted a Letter of Support for ENERATE, there is no need to reiterate the project's rationale. An email or telephone invitation for further collaboration should suffice.
- b) **Direct contact with stakeholders:** If a partner is already in regular communication with a stakeholder, the topic of engaging them as a stakeholder for ENERATE can be raised at a convenient time. While the potential stakeholder may have limited knowledge about ENERATE, establishing initial contact is unnecessary.
- c) **Engaging new stakeholders:** For stakeholders that are not part of regular communication channels, it's crucial to establish a communication channel and anticipate that they may have little or no knowledge of ENERATE, particularly for high-importance stakeholders. In this scenario, an initial dedicated face-to-face meeting is necessary.

1.4. Relation with other Work Packages

The stakeholder engagement process is not only crucial for the quality of the overall project but is also strictly connected to the other work packages, especially WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6 and WP7 since they will be determined to a large extent by the stakeholders' input.

- WP2- Requirements' Analysis and Specification of the ENERATE Platform

The work conducted in WP2 will need to have special attention to build the platform to the needs of the stakeholders identified. The activities outlined in the Engagement Plan here are part of the implementation of WP2 to define the use cases and need requirements from the stakeholders. WP2 has a timeline for engaging the pilot partners through a series of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to define these needs. This will establish the input requirements for the platform to be aligned with the needs of the different stakeholders. In a next step, WP2 will fine-tune these need requirements with external stakeholders through surveys.

The stakeholder mapping in WP5 impacts the activities of WP2 as it defines the categorisation of the stakeholders which WP2 will be using, while the engagement plan in WP5 provides an overview of the WP2 activities that are related to stakeholder engagement and how they're being followed up. This engagement is further described in Chapter 3.

- WP3- Design and Development of the ENERATE Platform

The relationship with this WP is especially accentuated in the “matchmaking process” (T.3.2) that aims to connect buyers (demand) and sellers (supply). To find appealing products, stakeholders must identify them based on their interests. Thus, this phase will help have a preliminary view of the matches that the platform will be able to create.

- WP4- Pilot assessments, Business model and Contractual Framework

The relationship with WP4 is due to the actions that will be implemented for the stakeholder's engagement plan during the pilot assessment. This task aims to evaluate how the ENERATE platform has helped to overcome obstacles in financing and energy efficient renovation and how it can be further developed for market uptake. The evaluation will include data analysis and feedback from platform users, as well as

benchmarking and impact assessment. This action will be further analyzed in chapter 3.

- WP6- Sustainability, Replication, and Exploitation of Project Results

One of the KPIs for achieving the main objective of this WP is to ensure that the results and findings gained within ENERATE are referenced by governance bodies in the targeted countries at least 10 times. Additionally, it is important to create bilateral exchange with at least 4 additional MSs governments or regulators on their national strategy for energy efficiency financing. The involvement of stakeholders is critical to achieving these KPIs because their inputs will be especially relevant for T.6.3, where policy recommendations based on the project results will be elaborated. If the platform successfully matches the needs of the stakeholders, the exploitation and replication of the project results will be successful, which will ultimately lead to greater uptake of energy efficiency financing strategies and practices across Europe.

- WP7- Dissemination, Communication and Awareness Creation

The objective of this task is to create a customized strategy and plan for dissemination and communication that effectively conveys the project key messages to its target audiences. A communication plan and stakeholder engagement mapping are closely connected since both aim to establish effective communication and engagement with stakeholders. The communication plan is then developed based on the mapping, considering the specific needs and preferences of each stakeholder group. The plan outlines the most effective channels, messages, and frequency of communication to reach the stakeholders, as well as the resources needed to implement it. Effective communication with stakeholders is crucial to the success of a project because it can help to build trust, create buy-in and support, and ensure that project goals are met. By connecting the communication plan to the stakeholder engagement mapping, project managers can tailor their communication strategies to the specific needs and expectations of each stakeholder group, increasing the likelihood of successful project outcomes.

2. Stakeholder Mapping

2.1. Stakeholder Identification

First, the stakeholder identification started with the establishment of the project purposes. Since ENERATE's goal is to create an efficient marketplace, the first categorization of stakeholders was made at first stage of the project development: The two main actors of the project were categorised as “supply” and “demand” side.

Figure 2. Stakeholder Mapping

These two groups constitute the “primary stakeholders”. Primary stakeholders are meant as those individuals or groups who have a direct and immediate interest in the activities or outcomes of a project. They are the ones who are most directly affected by the decisions and actions of the project.

Both stakeholder groups go back to the core of the ENERATE project, which is has as its main objective to bring together the building industry with the financing community through a match-making process within our platform. In our case the *supply*-side stakeholders are the building stakeholders, while the *demand*-side stakeholder belongs to the financing community.

2.1.1. Primary Stakeholders

- 1) **Supply-side stakeholders:** Stakeholders who are active in the building industry and can also be termed as *building stakeholders*. They have access to, or own data related to, one or more building projects and need to be able to easily declare the technical, commercial, and/or risk-related aspects of their building projects on the platform. Based on their inputs, the ENERATE platform can provide feedback on possible financing methods and make comparisons of KPIs with other building projects. The specific stakeholders identified within this group are:

- a) Energy Services Companies (ESCOs)
- b) Project Developers
- c) Building Owners & associations representing owners
- d) Asset Managers
- e) Energy Consultants

2) Demand-side stakeholders: Stakeholders who are market actors looking to use the ENERGATE platform for investment opportunities into building projects. They are more *financing stakeholders* who make use of the available data related to building projects to look for opportunities on where they can make investments through different types of methods, e.g. on-bill financing, project financing, leasing, ...
The stakeholders within this group are:

- a) Private Financing Bodies
- b) Public Financing Bodies
- c) Fund Managers
- d) Investment Consultants
- e) Private Investors
- f) Energy Services Companies (ESCOs)
- g) Project Developers

Some stakeholders such ESCOs and Project Developers, can be put into both categories as they have both access and/or own data of buildings and frequently look for the right investment opportunities for their services and projects. Given their impact on both sides, they are stakeholders that are crucial to be involved at every step of the engagement process.

2.1.2. Secondary Stakeholders

On the other hand, secondary stakeholders are those who have an indirect impact or more remote interest. They might not be able to directly use the platform but they're the type of stakeholders that can cause a spill-over effect in terms of sharing results and/or using the findings of the ENERGATE project for further research and innovation. As mentioned, the core objective of ENERGATE is to bring the building industry together with the financing community to increase the uptake of sustainability & energy efficiency investments into buildings. By doing this, the project works on the opportunities and barriers related to this process and can work with other stakeholders who have an interest in this to capitalise on the opportunities or overcome the barriers.

- a) Policymakers
- b) Policy support organisations
- c) Researchers & Academia
- d) Media
- e) Other EU project & initiatives

These stakeholders will mostly be involved through communication and dissemination activities in WP7 of ENERGATE and are not as much involved in the engagement plan that's elaborated for the other WPs. More information on how ENERGATE will try to reach them can be found in the ENERGATE Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1).

2.2. Analysis of stakeholder interest & influence

With the identification and categorisation of stakeholders we focus on this sub-chapter more on how why ENERGate is relevant for the different stakeholder groups by providing an overview of the key messages on why ENERGate is relevant for them. This has been setup in parallel with the Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1) where these key messages are relevant as well.

This is complemented by a “Power – Interest” analysis where REHVA, through a survey ([see Annex](#)), asked the consortium partners to provide their inputs on how “powerful” (how much influence) they had on the project results and how much “interest” they would potentially have in the project. As the consortium represents has a strong variety in expertise and interests, and many of the partners are part of the abovementioned stakeholder groups themselves, their answers could provide an overview at how the consortium perceives the importance and influence of the different stakeholder groups.

2.2.1. Why ENERGate is relevant for stakeholders

As mentioned, IEECP, REHVA and NTUA setup a table which briefly describes per identified stakeholder group why ENERGate is relevant for them. This helps to better understand on why the different stakeholders are relevant for ENERGate and why the project needs to engage them.

Table 1. Key messages per stakeholder group

Primary Stakeholders	
Supply-Side (Building) Stakeholder	
Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)	They can screen for new investment opportunities, learn from case studies, and provide data from their own services.
Project Developers	They can learn from the available data within the platform about the different financing methods for their projects. They can find funding entities interested in their projects.
Building owners	They can find funding entities in one single place. They can study other funded projects to improve their own application.
Asset Managers	They can learn about funding opportunities and better choose which funding entities to approach.
Demand-Side (Financial) Stakeholder	
Private financing Bodies	They can use the platform to learn from similar cases, thus reducing uncertainty and better estimating return.

Public Financing Bodies	They can use the platform to learn from similar cases and support decision-making.
Fund Managers	They can use information to support their decisions gaining information on risk assessment or return estimation. They can screen for new investment opportunities.
Investment Consultants	They can screen for new investment opportunities. Moreover, they can learn from case studies and better decide which types of projects are of interest to their clients.
Private Investors	The Information will be openly available in digestible formats and organized in a way that makes it easier for them to find interesting opportunities.
Secondary stakeholders	
Policy makers	They can get an overview of the market, thus adjusting future policies to the needs of all stakeholders.
Policy support organisations/ NGOs	They can access accurate and centralized information on funded EE projects, funding opportunities, and achieved outcomes. They can learn from case studies to improve their own work
Researchers and academia	They reap advantages from the spillover effects of data science results. Specifically, they may leverage the outcomes of data science activities to further their own research initiatives. Several decision support and multicriteria assessment techniques could be exploited in their own research.
Media	They can help increase public awareness, promote the marketplace, provide valuable feedback, and offer relevant expertise to support the project's success. Their role is essential to the work of WP7.
Other EU projects & initiatives	Similar to academia, they reap the advantages of the spillover effects of data science and building financing research outcomes that they can use to further build their own work on. ENERGATE can also feed into other initiatives and by doing so increase the multiplier effect of the project results.

2.2.2. Stakeholder Power – Interest Analysis

Prioritizing stakeholders based on their level of importance involves evaluating their interest and perceived ability to influence the project outcome. This can be achieved by ranking stakeholders as *low*, *medium*, or *high* based on their power and interest. The power-interest grid is a useful tool for stakeholder prioritization as it classifies stakeholders into four categories: high power/high interest, high power/low interest, low power/high interest, and low power/low interest.

REHVA conducted a survey ([see Annex](#)) among consortium partners to assess the power and interest levels of stakeholders, rating them from 1 to 5, with 1 being irrelevant/disinterested and 5 being very influential/interested. The analysis aimed to determine the perception of power and interest levels among the primary building and financial stakeholders in the consortium. It is worth noting that all stakeholders considered in this analysis are part of our “primary” stakeholders, and therefore none of them were categorized as having *low* power by the consortium.

The purpose of the analysis was to identify differences in the perceived levels of power and interest among stakeholders and after this to compare these findings with the current outreach potential of the consortium. This helps to identify potential opportunities and risks, as well as areas where more attention and engagement might be needed to build stronger relationships with these stakeholders.

The power-interest grid is a result of all partner's input, obtained through a survey among all project partners. This approach provides a balanced view from all partners' perspectives.

The role of each stakeholder according to their level in the power-interest grid can be described as follows:

- **High power, high interest stakeholders:** These stakeholders have a significant level of power and are highly interested in the project or issue. They may include key decision-makers and can have a significant impact on the success or failure of the project. It is important to engage and involve these stakeholders in the decision-making process.
- **High power, low interest stakeholders:** These stakeholders have a high level of power but may not be particularly interested in the project or issue. It is important to keep these stakeholders informed and engaged, but they may not require the same level of attention as high power, high interest stakeholders.
- **Low power, high interest stakeholders:** These stakeholders may not have significant power, but they are highly interested in the project or issue. It is important to engage and involve these stakeholders in the decision-making process, as they can provide valuable insights and feedback.
- **Low power, low interest stakeholders:** These stakeholders may have little power or interest in the project or issue. While it is important to keep these stakeholders informed, they may not require the same level of engagement as other stakeholders.

2.2.3. Power – Interest Grid Demand-Side (Financial) Stakeholders

Figure 3. Power - Interest Grid Demand-Side (Financial) Stakeholders

All stakeholder on the grid were identified earlier as important, hence why none of them are considered as having *low* power/influence, which has been confirmed by the answers of all the consortium partners. In the grid above we can see that **private investors** are assessed to have the lowest interest into the ENERGate platform. One of the reasons for this could be that private investors are the most wide-spread and varied group with strong varying priorities, and a large part of private investors are not formally connected to an organisation. This adds an additional challenge for ENERGate to mobilise them and reach out to them.

Fund managers are assessed as the most influential/powerful but with a medium interest into the project results. One important aspect with this stakeholder group is the financial size of the investment opportunities that will be available on the platform. Investment funds, as they are a collective of investors, will often only be interested in larger projects and their interest into the platform will depend on the size of the building projects available.

The Power – Interest balance looks the most interesting for **private financing bodies** where we note a *high* power, *high* interest. The ENERGate platform allows to examine building projects with a variety of financing methods and especially private financing bodies could be interested in this as they often aim for a more varied portfolio approach, especially if the projects are large enough. Different project partners also rated them quite high in interest as they have a stronger outreach to this target group, meaning that there’s a lot of potential to get relevant private financing bodies involved.

2.2.4. Power – Interest Grid Supply-Side (Building) Stakeholders

Figure 4. Power – Interest Grid Supply-Side (Building) Stakeholders

In general, the consortium expects a high interest from all supply-side stakeholders as they'll be able to use the ENERGate platform for a stronger data analysis of their building performance and find different financing methods for their building projects or services. This is often the largest obstacle for many building stakeholders and is precisely what the platform aims to address.

This is especially the case for **ESCOs** and **Project Developers**. ESCOs provide energy-efficient solutions to their clients and are often interested in exploring different financing methods that are available to make these solutions feasible. Matching specific building performance solutions with financing is precisely what the platform does, meaning that ESCOs are a perfect target group for the consortium to engage. Similar for project developers who need to implement the solutions, one of their biggest barriers often are related to the financing of the solutions.

As we will see in Chapter 2.3, the consortium has a stronger outreach to these types of stakeholders which explains why the confidence is higher that the project can engage with them in comparison to demand-side (financial) stakeholders.

2.3. Estimated outreach to Stakeholders Groups

Furthermore, another crucial step preceding the formulation of the engagement plan, involved determining the consortium's outreach potential. The grant agreement specified a minimum threshold of 350 key stakeholders, and to verify this number and devise the stakeholder engagement plan, the previously mentioned survey posed a query to the partners. Each project partner responded with their estimation of the number of potential primary stakeholders that they could reach in each country. We have put their answers into different pie charts to have a first overview of the outreach potential to different stakeholder within the consortium.

During the surveys the consortium estimated that it has an outreach to 382 primary stakeholders (which does not include the secondary stakeholders, see [Chapter 2.1.2](#)), 72 of them being financial stakeholders that belong to the demand-side segment which is described above ([Chapter 2.1](#)) and 310 are building stakeholders as part of the supply-side segment. This shows a strength on the supply-side in terms of stakeholders that can be engaged to provide data of their building projects & services. The biggest challenge will be to engage financial stakeholders and get them interested in capitalising in the financing opportunities that will be presented through the ENERGATE platform.

This is being complemented with a repository of stakeholder names and their contact details, which is being compiled by IEECP to feed into both WPs 5 and 7 activities to have a database of specific stakeholders that can be contacted during and after the project. This list will be continuously updated by all consortium partners. It cannot be shared in this document due to confidentiality but can be made available upon request.

Figure 5. Financial Stakeholders Consortium Outreach

As can be seen the consortium has a comparatively higher confidence in its outreach to private financing bodies than to the other stakeholders on the demand-side. This also explains why the consortium is slightly more confident that it can get private financing bodies interested and engaged with the project results (see [Chapter 2.2.3](#)). According to the survey most of the outreach to private financing bodies are situated in Greece (20 out of 31).

Outreach to public financing bodies is more limited as the EU-wide and national entities are often harder to involve for smaller financing projects, while the local/regional entities strongly depend on the contacts of the partners at such a geographical level. One of the core strengths of ENERGATE is the involvement of the Riga Planning Region (RPR) within the project who are also a pilot partner and can provide continuous feedback throughout the project from the perspective of a public financing body on the ENERGATE platform.

Furthermore, it is interesting to note the relatively strong outreach to fund managers, to which the consortium was more sceptical about their interest in the project results. Their interest will likely depend on the size of the financing opportunities available within the platform.

Figure 6. Building Stakeholders Consortium Outreach

The consortium has a significant presence among building stakeholders, more than financial stakeholders, with 90 project developers being the most prominent category. Project developers, together with ESCOs, are identified as stakeholders that can be both on the supply- and demand-side segment of the stakeholder groups (see [Chapter 2.1.1](#)) and they've been ranked as a very influential group (see [Chapter 2.2.4](#)) as they can both provide data and are interested in finding financing opportunities. Their combined number is 126 which shows a great potential to involve them in the ENERGATE results.

Building owners make up another significant category, with at least 46 representatives, as well as asset managers with 18. This shows that the consortium considers having a fairly strong outreach towards key decision-makers in the renovation process of buildings.

The strong outreach to building services engineers also suggests that the consortium is seeking to engage with stakeholders who can provide technical expertise, manage buildings and facilities, and help shape policy and regulations that could impact the energy efficiency marketplace.

Overall, the consortium's outreach strategy appears to be well-aligned with its goal. By engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders who can contribute technical expertise, decision-making authority, and financial resources, the consortium is likely to increase the chances of success for the project and drive adoption of energy efficiency solutions within the building sector.

Figure 7. Consortium Outreach by country

As we can see from the chart, the consortium will involve stakeholders from most areas of Europe, counting on stakeholders from West, North, South and East of Europe. This could help to ensure that the project outcomes are relevant and applicable across different contexts. Two partners, REHVA and IEECP, will reach out to stakeholders at EU level.

The country with the most project partners is Greece and thus, we expect to see this reflected on the stakeholder outreach. The partners which are responsible for the organisation of the four Regional Training Workshops (see [Chapter 3](#)) being Commuty (Spain), Enerbrain (Italy), RPR (Latvia) and GGGI (Hungary) also estimated to have a fairly strong outreach to different primary stakeholders.

With partners from several different countries across Europe, the ENERGATE project has the potential to have a significant impact at both the local and EU levels. Additionally, the involvement of partners such as REHVA and IEECP, which are focused on outreach at the EU level, suggests that the project will also have an impact beyond Greece and the other countries. These partners will work to engage stakeholders throughout Europe and share the results of the project more broadly. This means that the impact of the ENERGATE project has the potential to be felt across Europe, with benefits for energy efficiency and sustainability across the continent.

3. Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The engagement plan for the ENERGATE project consists of six actions to involve internal and external stakeholders continuously throughout the project. The preliminary plan has been laid down in the DoA which has been discussed during the Kick-off Meeting in January 2023 and further elaborated during subsequent online meetings in February – March 2023. The actions for engaging with stakeholders consists of:

1) M1 – M5: Surveys and semi-structured interviews with the pilot partners in the consortium (feeding into WP2)

The first action is co-creation of the platform, which includes receiving inputs from stakeholder groups to include the most recent, broad scope information, needs, and data into the platform to feed into WP2 (T2.1 & T2.3).

Flexiwatt, with support from NTUA, will prepare semi-structured interviews and a workshop with the 5 pilot partners. By early April, the first step in engaging with pilot partners will be to send them a questionnaire. The questionnaire will focus on identifying their needs, desired policy outcomes, and financial considerations to help define the project's requirements. During the first half of April, a preliminary presentation and guidelines for the use case methodology will be developed based on the questionnaire responses, while bilateral calls with the pilot partners will be organized to finalize the questionnaires and define user stories and use cases. By the end of April, the user stories and use cases will be fully defined. During the first half of May, additional bilateral calls with the pilot partners will be held to review the user stories and use cases. By the end of May, the functional and non-functional requirements for the project will be defined based on the input received from the questionnaire and bilateral discussions with the pilot partners.

This process will be further analysed in deliverable D2.2 Report on Specifications for Project Entries, User Profiles, Use Cases and User Ranks-v1.

The pilots within ENERGATE cover the primary stakeholders that have been described in Chapter 2 and represent both the supply- and demand-side needs to the ENERGATE platform. The pilots have been composed in such a way that they are both geographically varied and are representative for the primary stakeholder groups as how they've been explained under [Chapter 2.1](#) in this report. This allows for the ENERGATE project to continuously involve stakeholders who are part of the consortium with the project results in a co-design process. The table below shows which partners represent which stakeholder group:

Table 2. Pilot Projects

Partner	Country	Stakeholder group
Commuty	Spain	Asset Managers
RPR	Latvia	Public Fund
Greenesco	Greece	ESCOs
Enerbrain	Italy	Project developers & ESCOs
LDK	Greece	Building owners & energy consultants

These interviews have the objective to establish a first quality layer on the different use cases of the ENERGate platform to determine what are the requirements from the stakeholders to be able to use it. This information will feed into T2.2 on the *Definition of information entries to the ENERGate platform*. By assessing the needs of the internal stakeholders that are present within the consortium, the input requirements for front-end of the platform can be further determined.

2) M6 – M15: Surveys with external stakeholders

This is a more quantitative approach to get gather input from a larger variety of external stakeholders from all participating countries on their needs from the ENERGate platform. The surveys will be based on the results from semi-structured interviews and to further define the user-needs based on inputs from a larger group of stakeholders that are not part of the consortium. The external stakeholders will provide both an evaluation of the already defined user requirements based on the feedback from the pilots, and provide new user requirements where needed to fill the gap of missing points.

This survey can feed into WP3 as well by getting feedback on the first mock-ups of the platform. The survey will be setup by IEECP with support of REHVA and all partners will be responsible for gathering inputs from stakeholders within their own country. Flexiwatt will analyse the results to integrate into updated reports on the use cases (D2.5 & D2.6). The objective is to get the feedback from the key stakeholders within the network of the consortium.

3) M15 – M21: Series of webinars in partner countries

Following the surveys with external stakeholders, at least one webinar per partner country will be organised to present the mid-term results of the platform to a wider audience within the countries and gather their feedback for a final fine-tuning of the user requirements. IEECP and REHVA, as EU-wide organisations, will jointly organise an EU-wide webinar in English instead of a national webinar.

The webinars will on one side provide final feedback that can feed into the final user requirements report and already be a strong dissemination tool for sharing the results within all partners countries.

4) M6 – M30: Four Regional Training Workshops & Final Event

Four regional training workshops will be organized back-to-back with the project meetings to present the developments and outcomes of the project as well as go into detail on the platform's functionalities. The workshops will provide an overview of the ENERGate project, the platform's functionalities, barriers, scope, related activities, and common issues encountered during the implementation and roll-out of energy efficiency financing. Participants evaluation of the workshops will be collected through anonymous questionnaire responses, in order to help prepare the following workshop. Local consortium partners will support this task by sending invitations and recruiting participants through their local networks and established contacts. Since the workshops will be organised in sync with project meetings, key external experts will be invited to participate in Advisory board meetings with specific task leaders.

Table 3. Regional Training Workshops and Final Event

Date	Country	Organising Partner	Linked WPs
M9 (September 2023)	Spain	Commuty	WP2
M15 (After first release of the platform)	Italy	Enerbrain	WP2 & 3
M20 (Flexible date depending on progress)	Latvia	RPR	WP2 & 3
M25 (Depending on progress)	Hungary	GGGI	WP4 & 6
M30 (June 2025)	Belgium	REHVA	WP7 & All

The data obtained through this process will be utilized in the development of the final EU workshop event that will be spearheaded by REHVA in Brussels. This culminating event will serve as the foundation and groundwork for the project's future sustainability and platform, as well as the unveiling of forthcoming activities beyond the project's conclusion, drawing on the efforts of WP6 in generating recommendations and replication. If the opportunity presents itself, T6.2. can jointly organize the final event with other relevant projects, resulting in a more impactful and widespread message. The work conducted here is performed in close collaboration with the efforts of WP6.

5) M24 – M30: Pilot assessment with partners

The fourth action involves assessing the pilots from the perspective of stakeholders, including partner projects, linked platforms, and other relevant stakeholders/future users. This action is part of WP4, but it is closely connected to WP6. Its objective is to evaluate how the ENERGATE platform has helped overcome financing and energy efficiency renovation obstacles and promote market uptake. The assessment will include extensive data analysis and feedback from the pilot platform, resulting in a final methodological toolbox that includes a business model and a contractual framework. Specific actions include an internal analysis of the platform and stakeholder assessment to ensure appropriate buy-in and user-friendliness. The deliverable will validate draft pilots and standardised rule-based procedures for the operation of ENERGATE, as well as provide key recommendations on the contractual framework for platform deployment in a sustainable manner.

The last regional training workshop, hosted by GGGI, will be a crucial moment to discuss the lessons learned from the pilot assessment. Thus, GGGI's position will be critical in coordinating all connected tasks. This action will also be deeply linked to WP6 since the effectiveness of the platform tested with the pilots will determine the exploitation and sustainability of the project's results. The Replicability and Upscaling Strategy (RUS) aims to provide a plan for replicating and scaling up the ENERGATE platform in different target countries based on their level of involvement. Once the platform is more mature, processes will be set up to increase the inflow of building renovation projects from various sources, making the pilot assessment an essential phase of the engagement plan.

6) M6 – M30: Advisory Board meetings

The Advisory Board of the ENERGATE consortium is a crucial component of the project's interaction with stakeholders, bringing together 7 to 10 external experts with diverse expertise in various fields. These experts will be invited to attend the consortium meetings and participate in online meetings to provide guidance on specific topics that the project is working on. The Advisory Board members will represent a wide range of stakeholders, including asset managers, financial institutions such as banks, researchers, and policymakers. The expertise of the board members will be vital in shaping the direction of the project, providing valuable insights into the latest industry trends and best practices. The board members' input will help the ENERGATE consortium adapt the platform to the latest needs of the industry. With their collective knowledge and expertise, the Advisory Board will play a critical role in ensuring that the ENERGATE project achieves its goals and delivers tangible benefits to stakeholders.

Currently, at time of writing, the consortium – under coordination of IEECP - is putting together the Advisory Board members and inviting them to join.

4. Risks & Barriers

This section describes the possible risk and barriers that the project might encounter concerning the stakeholder's participation. Overall, identifying and engaging with stakeholders is a critical aspect of project development, and risks and barriers need to be carefully considered and managed to ensure project success.

Table 4. Risk and Barriers

Type of risk/barrier	Impact	Likelihood	Mitigation measure
Linguistic barriers with external stakeholders (outside of the consortium)	Stakeholders at local, regional & national level from outside of the consortium are planned to be engaged by the partners. For some stakeholders it might be difficult to participate actively in English workshops or fill in surveys which might hinder their feedback on the project results.	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The surveys with external stakeholders can be translated into the national language if the national partner considers it necessary. For the workshop, bilateral preparatory or follow-up meetings could be organised with the stakeholders where the national partners expect a language barrier.
Engaging with large-sized financial stakeholders	As analysed in Chapter 2.2.3 , the platform will first need to have attractive opportunities presented within the platform to get large financial stakeholders interested. Without these stakeholders, the end results will be more limited.	Medium	The consortium has a strong combination of both technical and financial expertise, meaning that the partners can input a significant amount of data and create opportunities that look attractive to get external stakeholders interested.
Resistance or lack of interest by stakeholders of targeted categories (e.g., financial sector, project developers, etc.)	Without their active participation, it will be difficult to gather their perspectives and feedback, which can lead to a platform that does not meet their needs	Medium	Consortium has already established links with relevant stakeholders and networks. More intensive focus will be given to the higher-level stakeholders, using more in depth and scientifically oriented arguments in order to persuade the potential

<p>in engaging in the dialogue process.</p>	<p>or expectations. This can result in a lack of adoption and utilization of the platform, ultimately hindering the achievement of the project's goals.</p>		<p>organisations' representatives to join the ENERATE dialogue process. Consortium will keep the dialogue with the stakeholders who are low-responsive or show lack of interest, to try to recover the relationship and keep collaborating to the ENERATE activities. Targeted dissemination and communication activities will take place according to each stakeholder category needs.</p>
<p>Different interests among stakeholders which can hinder the platform usability</p>	<p>Building stakeholders such as ESCOs, project developers, building owners, and asset managers may have different levels of interest in the project and may be difficult to engage effectively. For example, smaller building owners may not have the resources or expertise to participate fully in the platform, while larger asset managers may have their own proprietary systems for managing energy efficiency.</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>At a technical level, the project will need to ensure that the platform can be adapted to the needs of different types of stakeholders. Activities in WP5 are precisely aimed in getting feedback from multiple stakeholders so that the platform development in WPs 2 & 3 can be adapted accordingly.</p>
<p>Limited participation in the events (e.g., Regional Training Workshops) of stakeholders in general and more specifically of experts from countries beyond the consortium countries.</p>	<p>This risk can have a significant impact on the overall success of the platform. The lack of participation from stakeholders, particularly experts from countries beyond the consortium countries, may result in insufficient feedback for the platform's development. This can ultimately lead to a platform that is not user-friendly and does</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Partners have strong links with regional / local authorities and networks from H2020 initiative but not limited; these links will be exploited by ENERATE. Dissemination and communication actions (newsletters, social media, website announcements etc.) and posts in several platforms visited by key target groups, such as BUILD UP, Construction 21, the UNEP Finance Initiative etc. will further promote stakeholder participation in workshops. A more flexible schedule shall be</p>

	not meet the needs of stakeholders, resulting in low adoption rates.		adopted for all, if not the majority, of the involved stakeholders in each country to be able to join (in terms of time plan and means of realisation due to the unforeseen circumstances of covid-19). A confirmation ratio of 70% will be taken into consideration in order to ensure targeted size of events. The combination of all these measured is expected to minimise the risks.
Stakeholders may not dedicate enough time to address the ENERGATE activities and meeting the input deadlines.	Without timely and meaningful input from stakeholders, the project may not be able to effectively address their needs and provide relevant solutions.	Medium	The ENERGATE involved partner will strengthen its support to the stakeholder and optimise (i.e., reduce) the time required to the stakeholder with a continuous support to their cooperative work. The required steps will be clearly explained and each possible question or doubt from the stakeholder will be promptly addressed to allow them to complete their collaborative activities in due time. A possible slight delay can be taken into consideration, provided that this delay does not have a critical impact on the project activities
Stakeholders which are successfully engaged may be concerned about sharing sensitive information related data etc., because this information are considered sensitive for their production process	If stakeholders are not willing to share information, it can limit the effectiveness of the platform and its ability to provide meaningful insights and solutions.	Low	Stakeholders will be ensured ENERGATE compliance with the current EU legislation on data privacy and security and about the confidentiality of the deliverables that will include the stakeholders' input.

5. Final Conclusions

On one side, we have looked at stakeholder mapping. We first analysed who the primary stakeholders were based on the preliminary proposal phase and an open discussion during the project Kick-off Meeting and online follow-up meetings. The primary stakeholders can be divided into two segments: **supply-side** and **demand-side**. This division is essential because the key interest of the stakeholder depends on which segment they belong to. The supply-side strongly overlaps with stakeholders situated in the building industry, such as ESCOs, project developers, building owners, and asset managers, who have access to, or own data related to buildings. The demand-side stakeholders mostly overlap with financial actors who can use the ENERGATE platform to find attractive investment opportunities within the building industry.

After this we assessed the potential “power” and “interest” of the primary stakeholders into the ENERGATE project and put them on a “Power – Interest Grid”. This grid was established based on an internal survey that REHVA conducted with all consortium partners. In this grid we could see that fund manager could potentially have a big impact on the project due to the large portfolios they often control but could be more challenging to get interested as they are mostly interested in larger financing project. The same is true for public financing bodies. The most potential could be seen with private financing bodies in terms of interest and power, this mostly related to the larger outreach potential that the consortium has to this target group.

For the building stakeholders it was important to note that the consortium assessed that both ESCOs and project developers had a high potential in both interest and power. This can be explained since both stakeholders are part of the consortium, are related to both the demand- and supply-side segments and the consortium considers having a fairly strong outreach to these target groups.

On the other side, an engagement plan to reach to these stakeholders has been established which combines different types of activities. First there are the activities which involves stakeholders who are part of the ENERGATE consortium and represent most of the primary stakeholders. Through semi-structured interviews and surveys, the relevant partners will give inputs and feedback on their expectations and needs of the ENERGATE platform. This activity corresponds with T2.3 and will feed into WP2 to help further determine the platform typologies and use cases.

This will be followed by a more quantitative approach where surveys will be shared with external stakeholders, outside of the consortium, where the first results of the platform will be shared and we will ask for additional inputs from a larger pool of stakeholders. This step will be used to get first feedback on the platform mock-ups and ensure that it is adapted to a larger variety of stakeholders.

In parallel with these steps four Regional Training Workshops will be organised in Spain, Italy, Latvia and Hungary. This is again a more qualitative approach but with external stakeholders this time. These workshops will allow to get more in-depth information about the needs of the different stakeholders at different national & regional levels, which is needed to make the platform suitable in different geographical contexts.

For the last step of the engagement plan, the perspective will be again turned to the internal stakeholders in the consortium. Pilot assessments will be carried out under T4.3 to get a more in-depth understanding of the pilots and what lessons ENERGATE can learn out of this. An analysis will be made from the pilot experiences, which will be part of the fourth Regional Training Workshop in Hungary (M24) and where the lessons will be presented to external

stakeholders who can provide feedback on this for the final adaptations of the ENERGATE platform.

6. Annex

Survey to consortium partners.

ENERGATE WP5- Stakeholder mapping: Questionnaire for Partners

ENERGATE WP5- Stakeholder mapping: Questionnaire for Partners

This questionnaire is a part of D5.1 the "Stakeholder Mapping & Engagement Plan". In order to proceed with this we need an overview of the outreach that all partners have to different types of stakeholders, this is especially relevant for the pilot countries but for the rest of the consortium as well. Involving the right stakeholders is crucial to gain feedback for the platform and obtain project results that align with their needs on one hand (feeding into WP2 - 4), and allow us to better disseminate the project results on the other (feeding into WP7). Before starting the questionnaire a reminder of what is meant as supply- and demand-side type of stakeholders:

Supply side stakeholders are the groups that have access and/or own data about buildings and can provide data inputs into the platform. For example asset managers, building owner, ESCOs, project developers...

Demand side stakeholders are more the "financial" type of stakeholders who are looking for attractive financial packages provided through the platform. For example private & public financing bodies, investment consultants, fund managers, ...

Please indicate your organisation *

Please indicate your organisation's country *

DO YOU HAVE A STRONG OUTREACH TO ANY THE FOLLOWING DEMAND-SIDE (/FINANCIAL) STAKEHOLDERS? *

You can select multiple options.

 PRIVATE FINANCING BODIES

<input type="checkbox"/>	PUBLIC FINANCING BODIES
<input type="checkbox"/>	FUND MANAGERS
<input type="checkbox"/>	INVESTMENT COUNSULTANTS
<input type="checkbox"/>	PRIVATE INVESTORS
<input type="checkbox"/>	NONE OF THE ABOVE
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other

COULD YOU GIVE US AN ESTIMATE OF THE NUMBER OF STAKEHOLDERS PER SUB-CATEGORY YOU WOULD BE ABLE TO INVOLVE FOR AN INTERVIEW AND/OR WORKSHOP:

Enter a number (0 is a relevant answer as well).

PRIVATE FINANCING BODIES	<input type="text"/>
PUBLIC FINANCING BODIES	<input type="text"/>
FUND MANAGERS	<input type="text"/>
INVESTMENT CONSULTANTS	<input type="text"/>
PRIVATE INVESTORS	<input type="text"/>
OTHER FINANCIAL STAKEHOLDERS (SPECIFY WHICH)	<input type="text"/>

How would you rate the interest of the following financial stakeholders in the project?

Private Financing Bodies

Disinterested					Very interested
1	2	3	4	5	

Public Financing bodies

Disinterested					Very interested
1	2	3	4	5	

Fund Managers

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Investment Consultants

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Private Investors

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

How would you rate the influence of the following financial stakeholders in the project outcome?

Private Financing Bodies

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Public Financing Bodies

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Fund Managers

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Investment Consultants

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Private Investors

Neutral/ Irrelevant

Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Do you have any remarks on the influence or interest of financial stakeholders?

DO YOU HAVE A STRONG OUTREACH TO ANY OF THE FOLLOWING SUPPLY-SIDE (/BUILDING) STAKEHOLDERS? *

You can select multiple options.

ESCOs

PROJECT DEVELOPERS

BUILDING OWNERS

ASSET MANAGERS

NONE OF THE ABOVE

Other

COULD YOU GIVE US AN ESTIMATE OF THE NUMBER OF STAKEHOLDERS PER SUB-CATEGORY YOU WOULD BE ABLE TO INVOLVE FOR AN INTERVIEW AND/OR WORKSHOP:

ESCOs	
PROJECT DEVELOPERS	
BUILDING OWNERS	
ASSET MANAGERS	
OTHER BUILDING STAKEHOLDER (SPECIFY WHICH)	

How would you rate the interest of the following building stakeholders in the project?

ESCOs

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Project Developers

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Building Owners

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Asset Managers

Disinterested Very interested

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

How would you rate the influence of the following building stakeholders in the project outcome?

ESCOs

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Project Developers

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Building Owners

Neutral/ Irrelevant Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Asset Managers

Neutral/ Irrelevant

Very influential

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Do you have any remarks on the influence or interest of building stakeholders?

DO YOU HAVE A STRONG OUTREACH TO ANY OF THE FOLLOWING SECONDARY STAKEHOLDERS? *

You can select multiple options.

POLICY MAKERS

POLICY SUPPORT ORGANISATIONS/ NGOs

RESEARCHERS AND ACADEMIA

MEDIA

NONE OF THE ABOVE

Other

THANK YOU FOR COMPLETING THE SURVEY!

OUR TEAM

See you online!

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